

18 **Keywords:**

19 bridgmanite; grain growth; lower mantle

20 **Highlight:**

21 The grain size exponent for growth of bridgmanite in post-spinel is 5.2 ± 0.3 .

22 The activation enthalpy for grain growth of bridgmanite is 260 ± 20 kJ/mol.

23 Grain size of bridgmanite is $\sim 30\text{-}45$ μm in cold subducted slabs with 1-10 Myr age.

24 **1. Introduction:**

25 Grain size of minerals is a fundamental parameter that affect geodynamic processes in the Earth's
26 interior because it controls the physical and chemical properties of mineral aggregates including
27 creep law, diffusive element transportation, seismic attenuation, and chemical mixing (e.g.
28 Dannberg et al., 2017; Hirth and Kohlstedt, 2003; Faul and Jackson, 2007; 2015; Jackson et al.,
29 2002; Lau and Faul, 2019; Solomatov and Reese, 2008; ten Grotenhuis et al., 2004). Knowledge
30 about grain size in the Earth's interior is therefore vital to understand mantle dynamics
31 (Dannberg et al., 2017).

32 The deformation mechanism in the lower mantle is dominated by either dislocation creep or
33 diffusion creep. The absence of strong seismic anisotropy suggested that diffusion creep is more
34 prevalent in the majority of lower mantle (e.g. Meade et al., 1995). While dislocation creep is
35 independent of grain size, diffusion creep is inversely proportional to d^2 (Nabarro-Herring creep)

36 or d^3 (Coble creep), where d is the average grain size. Therefore, the viscosity in the lower mantle
37 will have a strong grain size dependence. Grain size is thus a key parameter that required for
38 investigation of lower mantle rheology.

39 Because of the lack of natural samples, it is impossible to know the grain size distribution in the
40 lower mantle directly. Instead, it can be inferred from the history of lower-mantle rocks. There
41 are three processes that affect grain size in the lower mantle. 1) Solidification in the terrestrial
42 magma ocean. 2) Grain size reduction to nearly zero by phase transition across the phase
43 boundaries, i.e., dissociation of ringwoodite to bridgmanite + ferropericlase at the 660-km
44 seismic discontinuity driven by the downward flow. 3) Grain growth over the geological time after
45 the solidification or phase transition. Therefore, if the whole mantle convection occurs, the grain
46 sizes of the downward flows of in the lower mantle can be estimated by the grain growth kinetics
47 with an initial grain size of zero due to the phase transition at 660-km depth. On the other hand,
48 if two-layer convection dominates, the grain size will follow the growth rate with initial grain size
49 upon the origin of the rocks, e.g. formed during the solidification from magma ocean.
50 Investigation of grain growth kinetics is thus important for understanding the properties and
51 dynamics of the lower mantle.

52 Grain growth kinetics of the major upper-mantle minerals have been extensively studied (e.g.,
53 Guignard et al., 2012; 2016; Hiraga et al., 2010; Karato et al., 1989; Nichols and Mackwell, 1991;
54 Nishihara et al., 2006; Tsujino and Nishihara, 2009; Yamazaki et al., 2005). Generally, they follow
55 a power-law relationship of,

$$56 \quad d^n - d_0^n = kt \quad (1)$$

57 where d and d_0 are the final and initial grain sizes, respectively, n is the grain size exponent
58 (coarsening exponent), t is duration, and k is the growth rate constant, which is pressure and
59 temperature dependent. The n exponent determines the grain size evolution with time ($d \propto t^{1/n}$
60 when $d_0 \ll d$). Values of 2~5 have been often observed in single phase or polymineralic system
61 of mantle minerals (e.g., Guidard et al., 2016; Hiraga et al., 2010; Nichols and Mackwell, 1991;
62 Yamazaki et al., 2005).

63 In contrast to the upper mantle, the grain growth kinetics of lower mantle minerals are poorly
64 constrained. Yamazaki et al. (1996; 2009) investigated the grain growth of bridgmanite (and
65 periclase) at a pressure of 25 GPa and temperatures of 1570-2170 K and reported an extremely
66 large value of n (10~11). However, they used very fine-grained (<1 μm) Fe-free forsterite powder
67 as a starting material, which always contains some amounts of absorbed water. Such absorbed
68 water may enhance the grain growth of minerals significantly (e.g. Jung and Karato, 2001;
69 Nishihara et al., 2006). Additionally, the grain growth rate of the Fe-free sample might be largely
70 different from Fe-bearing ones (e.g. Yamazaki et al., 2005) and should be more appropriate to
71 simulate the lower mantle. Furthermore, the non-hydrostaticity in Yamazaki et al. (1996; 2009)
72 may affect the grain growth kinetics due to the dynamic recrystallization (Jung and Karato, 2001).
73 Considering the nearly hydrostatic conditions in the Earth's mantle (stress at the level of 0.1~1
74 MPa estimated from velocity of plate motion), experiments should be performed with minimized
75 differential stress.

76 Solomatov et al. (2002) modeled the grain size evolution in the bridgmanite-ferropericlase two
77 phase system by Monte Carlo simulation. Nevertheless, their simulations were performed based

78 on the assumptions of $n = 4$ for a grain-boundary diffusion-controlled grain growth kinetics and
79 $n = 3$ for a lattice diffusion-controlled process. Therefore, there is a significant gap between the
80 experimental results and numerical simulations.

81 In this study, we investigated the grain growth kinetics of Fe-bearing bridgmanite that coexists
82 with ferropericlase. The grain size of bridgmanite was measured as a function annealing duration
83 and temperature. We also examined the effects of absorbed water and iron content. The
84 experiments were performed at a pressure of 27 GPa with minimized stress conditions, which is
85 smaller than 10 MPa (Rubie et al., 1993).

86 **2. Experimental and analytical methods**

87 **2.1 Starting material**

88 Hand-picked inclusion-free San Carlos olivine $[(\text{Mg}_{1.82}\text{Fe}_{0.18})\text{SiO}_4]$ single crystals were used as a
89 starting material in the majority of runs. The single crystals were ground to a powder with grain
90 sizes of 1-10 μm and stored in a vacuum furnace at 400 K before use. Additionally, a piece of Fe-
91 free forsterite single crystal $[\text{Mg}_2\text{SiO}_4]$, impurity described in Fei et al. (2012)) was used to
92 examine the iron effect.

93 **2.2 Sample syntheses of high-pressure phase assemblages**

94 Bridgmanite samples coexisting with ferropericlase were synthesized from the San Carlos olivine
95 powder using a multi-anvil press. Multiple layers of olivine powder separated by Fe foils were
96 loaded into a Pt capsule with outer and inner diameters of 1.0 and 0.8 mm, respectively. The

97 thickness of each layer was about 150 μm (Fig. 1a). Tiny amounts of Fe-FeO (IW buffer) was
98 loaded next to the Fe foils to fix the oxygen fugacity (f_{O_2}). The capsule was loaded into a 7/3
99 standard multi-anvil cell assembly at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut with a LaCrO_3 furnace, a Cr_2O_3 -
100 doped MgO octahedron with 7-mm edge length, and a D-type W/Re thermocouple (Fig. 1).

101 The completed whole assembly was dried in a vacuum furnace at 400 K for over 24 hours.
102 Afterwards, it was compressed to 27 GPa at room temperature by 8 pieces of tungsten carbide
103 cubes with 26-mm edge lengths and 3-mm truncation edge lengths using a 15-MN multi-anvil
104 press with the Osugi-type guide block at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut (Ishii et al., 2019). After
105 reaching the desired pressure, the assembly was heated to 1700 K with a ramping rate of ~ 50
106 K/min. After keeping the temperature at 1700 K for 5 min, the assembly was quenched to room
107 temperature by switching off the heating power and decompressed slowly to ambient pressure
108 over more than 15 hours.

109 Finally, well-sintered and homogeneously distributed aggregates of bridgmanite-ferropericlase
110 mixtures (hereafter post-spinel) with grain sizes less than 0.1 μm were obtained (Fig. 2). Each
111 layer was mechanically broken into small pieces with 100-200 μm in size using a razor under an
112 optical microscope. The small pieces were used as samples in the following grain growth
113 experiments.

114 **2.3 Grain-growth experiments**

115 In each grain growth run, pieces of the synthesized post-spinel aggregates were embedded in a
116 pre-dried CsCl powder within Pt capsule, which provided quasi-hydrostatic conditions (e.g., Fei

117 et al., 2017). A Fe-FeO powder (IW buffer) was loaded at the two ends of Pt capsule to buffer the
118 f_{O_2} . The capsule was loaded into the standard 7/3 multi-anvil assembly again (Fig. 1b), and dried
119 in a desiccator before compression. The grain growth runs were performed at a pressure of 27
120 GPa and temperatures of 1400 to 2400 K following the same compression and heating procedure
121 as that for sample synthesis experiment. The annealing durations of the grain growth runs were
122 from 1.5 to 1000 min as listed in Table 1.

123 To examine possible effects of Fe content and absorbed water in Yamazaki et al. (1996)'s
124 experiments, three additional runs (I1105, I1143, I1147 in Table 1) were performed at a pressure
125 of 27 GPa and a temperature of 2200 K for 2-300 min of annealing duration. In these runs, two
126 capsules were loaded in the same assembly. The first capsule was filled with San Carlos olivine
127 powder, which is expected to contain absorbed water. The second capsule contained multiple
128 pieces of samples embedded in CsCl, i.e., pre-synthesized post-spinel aggregates, San Carlos
129 olivine single crystal, and Fe-free forsterite single crystal.

130 **2.4 Grain-size measurements**

131 The recovered samples were carefully taken out from CsCl by dissolving it in water, mounted
132 and polished by emery papers and 0.25 μm diamond pastes, and imaged using a scanning
133 electron microscope (SEM) with acceleration voltages of 5 to 20 kV. The grains were hand-traced
134 in the BSE images and the area of each bridgmanite grain was obtained by image processing
135 software ImageJ (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/>). The diameter of each grain was calculated from the
136 area by approximating the grain shape by a circle. More than three BSE images from different

137 regions of each sample were analyzed, for a total of more than 300 bridgmanite grains. The grain
138 size of ferropericlase was not investigated in this study.

139 **3. Experimental results**

140 **3.1 Grain size distribution**

141 Bridgmanite and ferropericlase phases are clearly distinguished by brightness contrast in back-
142 scattered electron (BSE) images. Bridgmanite grains have sharp grain boundaries and 120°-angle
143 triple junctions (e.g. Fig. 3). No clearly heterogeneous grain size distribution was found. With a
144 sufficiently large number (>300) of analyzed grains for each sample, the grain sizes in log unit
145 ($\log d$) show a relatively narrow and symmetric Gaussian distributions (Fig. 3). The mean values
146 and standard deviations of $\log d$ were thus obtained from the Gaussian distributions and listed in
147 Table 1.

148 **3.2 Grain size exponent**

149 Examples of BSE images obtained from samples annealed at the same pressure (27 GPa) and
150 temperature (2200 K) conditions but with different durations are shown in Fig. 3. The grain size
151 of bridgmanite systematically increases from 0.42 μm to 0.72, 1.08, and 1.69 μm with increasing
152 duration from 1.5 min to 10, 100, and 1000 min, respectively. The $\log d$ of bridgmanite was
153 plotted against $\log t$ in Fig. 4. Overall, $\log d$ is found to be linearly correlated with $\log t$. Because d_0
154 ($<0.1 \mu\text{m}$) is negligible in comparison with d , the data points are fit to equation (1) in the form of,

$$155 \left(\frac{\partial(\log d)}{\partial(\log t)} \right)_T = \frac{1}{n} \quad (2)$$

156 and a grain size exponent of $n = 5.2 \pm 0.3$ is obtained by the least square fitting.

157 **3.3 Grain growth rate constant**

158 For experiments performed with the same duration (1000 min), at a range of temperature
159 conditions, the grain size of bridgmanite increases from 0.33 to 1.72 μm with increasing
160 temperature from 1400 to 2200 K (Fig. 5). Grain growth rate constants (k) were calculated from
161 Eq. (1) with the above determined grain size exponent of 5.2 and the results are listed in Table 1.
162 The values of k are plotted as a function of temperature in Fig. 6. Since grain growth is a kinetic
163 process, k should follow the Arrhenius relation,

$$164 \quad k = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

165 where k is in $\mu\text{m}^n/\text{s}$, k_0 is the pre-exponential factor, ΔH is the activation enthalpy, R is the ideal
166 gas constant, and T is absolute temperature. Least squares fitting to Eq. (2) yields $\log k_0$ ($\mu\text{m}^n/\text{s}$) =
167 2.6 ± 0.4 and $\Delta H = 260 \pm 20$ kJ/mol.

168 **4. Discussion**

169 **4.1 Comparison with previous studies**

170 The grain size exponent determined in this study is 5.2 ± 0.3 . It is much smaller than that
171 determined by Yamazaki et al. (1996), which was 10.6 ± 1.1 (Fig. 4). Namely, the grain size of
172 bridgmanite has much stronger time-dependence than previously thought. This difference
173 should not be caused by experimental uncertainty, because the scatters of $\log d$ are within 0.1

174 log unit in both this study and in Yamazaki et al. (1996), whereas the difference between this
175 study and Yamazaki et al. (1996) is larger than 0.3 log unit in short-duration experiments (Fig. 4).

176 As explained in the introduction section, the extremely large n obtained by Yamazaki et al. (1996)
177 could be caused by the effects of absorbed water and/or iron because they used fine-grained Fe-
178 free forsterite powder samples. To examine our hypotheses, the I1105, I1143, and I1147 were
179 performed with multiple samples in each run (Table 1). Because the multiple samples should
180 experience exactly the same P - T condition and the same duration in each run, they can be directly
181 compared with minimized experimental uncertainties. As shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, the samples
182 initially from the olivine single crystal and from the pre-synthesized post-spinel have exactly the
183 same grain sizes. This is reasonable because both of them are dry and have the same composition.
184 When the annealing duration is short (2 and 5 mins in I1147 and I1105, respectively), the samples
185 from the olivine powder have larger grain sizes than those from pre-synthesized post-spinel. In
186 contrast, when the heating duration is long (300 min in I1143), the difference diminished. Fe-free
187 forsterite single crystal sample has smaller grain size than iron-bearing system, indicating that
188 presence of Fe enhances the grain growth of bridgmanite.

189 The $\log d$ vs. $\log t$ from forsterite single crystals indicates $n = 5.5 \pm 0.4$, which is identical to the Fe-
190 bearing system, but smaller than the value of 10.6 ± 1.1 determined by Yamazaki et al. (1996)
191 with forsterite powder as the starting material (Fig. 8). Our olivine powder samples show $n = 9.7$
192 ± 0.6 (dot line in Fig. 8), which is much larger than the pre-synthesized post-spinel samples and
193 comparable with Yamazaki et al. (1996). Therefore, we interpret that, when powder samples
194 were used, the grain growth was significantly enhanced by absorbed water in short duration

195 experiments, but such an effect diminished in long duration experiments due to sample
196 dehydration. As a result, the grain size exponent was apparently enlarged. Because the Pt
197 capsules were not welded, water should have escaped from the capsules continuously, therefore,
198 the $\log d$ vs. $\log t$ relation should be curved (dashed line in Fig. 8). Since the powder used in
199 Yamazaki et al. (1996) had less than 1- μm particle size, and our olivine powder is 1-10 μm , the
200 absorbed water will be different by a factor of ~ 10 by assuming the one order of magnitude
201 difference in particle size. Using the water exponent of 1.7 of a wet system (Nishihara et al., 2006),
202 the grain size could be raised by ~ 0.33 log units, which explains the discrepancy of $\log d$ between
203 this study and Yamazaki et al. (1996). Of course the above scenario is our interpretation based
204 on Fig. 8 and the exact reason for the discrepancy is unknown. It nevertheless well explains the
205 discrepancy of both n and $\log d$ and therefore we believe it is the most convincing reason.

206 **4.2 Grain growth mechanisms**

207 Theoretically, the grain growth of polycrystalline aggregates occurs by the migration of grain
208 boundaries. It should be controlled by the atomic diffusion of the slowest elements. In two-phase
209 systems, the grain size exponents are generally $n = 3$ when grain growth is controlled by lattice
210 diffusion, $n = 4$ when controlled by grain-boundary diffusion, and $n \geq 5$ when controlled by
211 diffusion along dislocations (pipe diffusion) (Atkinson, 1988; Ardell, 1972; Brook, 1976).
212 Additionally, the elastic stress in high-pressure experiments may also affect the value of grain
213 size exponent (Solomatov et al., 2002).

214 Because the samples were surrounded by CsCl in this study, the non-hydrostatic stress should be
215 minimal, i.e., resulting in annihilation of dislocations. Therefore, the dislocation density should

216 be extremely low (Fei et al., 2017). Thus, the grain growth mechanism in this study with $n = 5.2 \pm$
217 0.3 should not be influenced by stress or dislocation-controlled diffusion. Hiraga et al. (2010)
218 reported a value of $n \approx 5$ in the forsterite-enstatite system, which is comparable as the n
219 determined in this study for the bridgmanite-ferropericlasite system. They found that the
220 experimentally measured grain growth rates in the forsterite-enstatite system are comparable
221 with those simulated from Si grain-boundary diffusion coefficients. Therefore, they concluded
222 that grain-boundary diffusion controlled grain growth even though the grain size exponent is n
223 ≈ 5 . Considering the grain size exponent of $n = 5.2 \pm 0.3$ determined in this study and that it is
224 unlikely that stress or dislocation-controlled diffusion influenced the growth rates as explained
225 above, we conclude that the grain growth process of bridgmanite in this study is controlled by
226 the grain boundary diffusion as well. Therefore, k should be proportional to D^{gb} , where D^{gb} is the
227 grain boundary diffusion coefficient of the slowest species.

228 The Mg grain boundary diffusion coefficient in bridgmanite is unknown, but it is expected to be
229 similar to Si, because they have nearly identical lattice diffusion coefficients (Dobson et al., 2008;
230 Holzapfel et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2011; Yamazaki et al., 2000). On the other hand, the oxygen grain-
231 boundary diffusion is 3-4 orders of magnitude faster than Si (Dobson et al., 2008; Yamazaki et al.,
232 2000). Thus, Si and Mg should be the rate-limiting species for grain growth of bridgmanite. This
233 is also suggested by the comparable activation enthalpy for Si grain boundary diffusion ($\Delta H = 310$
234 ± 50 kJ/mol determined in Yamazaki et al., 2000), for grain-boundary controlled anelastic process
235 (286 kJ/mol, Lau and Faul, 2019), and for grain growth process ($\Delta H = 260 \pm 20$ kJ/mol determined
236 in this study).

237 **4.3 Grain size at the topmost lower mantle**

238 Although the grain size of bridgmanite in Yamazaki et al., (1996) is larger than that of the present
239 study in the investigated annealing durations (Fig. 4), the relations will be reversed with longer
240 duration due to their large grain growth exponent. The crossover will occur at an annealing time
241 of $\sim 10^4$ - 10^5 min (10^1 - 10^2 days). The grain size of bridgmanite at geological time scales should
242 therefore be much larger than previously considered.

243 Because of the phase transformation across the 660-km discontinuity in subducted slabs, the
244 grain size of bridgmanite in the topmost lower mantle can be estimated based on the grain
245 growth rate determined in this study and initial grain size of zero due to the phase transformation.
246 By assuming a slab geotherm of 1600 K at 700 km depth [400 K lower than the mantle geotherm
247 (e.g. Fukao et al., 2009; Schmid et al., 2006)], over a geological time of 1-10 Myr (corresponding
248 to tens to hundreds kilometer subduction depth), the grain size of bridgmanite will be 30~45 μ
249 m (Fig. 8). It is about 0.5 order of magnitude larger than that calculated from Yamazaki et al.
250 (1996) (~ 10 μ m for 1-10 Myr age at 1600 K) (Fig. 8). Consequently, since diffusion creep is
251 inversely proportional to $d^2 \sim d^3$, the diffusion creep rate in the slabs mantle should be 1~1.5
252 orders of magnitude lower than that estimated using Yamazaki et al. (1996)'s results.

253 The grain size in the ambient mantle will follow the growth rate with an initial grain size
254 determined by the origin and history of the rocks. If we assume the minimum case, i.e., initial
255 grain size of zero, over a geological time of 100 Myr – 1 Gyr at the topmost lower mantle
256 temperature [2000 K, Katsura et al., 2010)], the grain size will be 150-230 μ m (Fig. 9). It is larger

257 than the subducted slabs by a factor of $3\sim 10$. The grain size effect will therefore increase the
258 diffusion creep rate of slabs at least by one order of magnitude in comparison with the ambient
259 mantle. On the other hand, the observations of seismic anisotropies around slabs imply the
260 contribution of dislocation creep in these regions (e.g. Foley and Long, 2011; Lynner and Long,
261 2014; Meade et al., 1995). Namely, the contribution of dislocation creep will further lower the
262 slab strength. Therefore, the subducted slabs are expected to be softer than ambient mantle.
263 This could be one reason that some subducted slabs stagnate below the 660-km discontinuity
264 (e.g. Fukao et al., 2013).

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359 **Fig captions:**

360 **Fig. 1.** Cross-sections of the cell assemblies used in this study. (a) for the sample synthesis
361 experiment. (b) for grain growth experiments. Multiple layers of post-spinel (bridgmanite +
362 ferropericlase) were synthesized from olivine powder using the assembly shown in (a). Each layer
363 of the synthesized samples from (a) was cut into a number of pieces (each piece 100~200 μm in
364 size). The pieces were used for the grain growth experiments in (b).

365 **Fig. 2.** Synthesized post-spinel for grain growth runs. Because of bridgmanite amorphousization,
366 it is unable to take high magnification images for statistic analysis of grain size. but it is clearly
367 less than 0.1 μm , which is much smaller than those after grain growth runs as listed in Table 1.

368 **Fig. 3.** BSE images (left) and grain size distributions (right) of the samples annealed at the same
369 pressure and temperature conditions (27 GPa, 2200 K), but different run durations (1.5 to 1000
370 min). The grain size of bridgmanite (dark grains) show relatively narrow and symmetric Gaussian
371 distributions. The average grain size (\bar{d}) increases systematically with increasing annealing
372 duration. High resolution BSE images are given in the online Supplementary Material.

373 **Fig. 4.** Bridgmanite grain size evolution with time at 1400-2400 K. The slope of the fitting lines
374 represents $1/n$ in Eq. (2).

375 **Fig. 5.** BSE images (left) and grain size distributions (right) of the samples annealed at 27 GPa with
376 the same run duration (1000 min), but different temperatures (1400 – 2200 K). The average grain
377 size (\bar{d}) increases systematically with increasing temperature. High resolution BSE images are
378 given in the online Supplementary Material.

379 **Fig. 6.** The grain growth rate of bridgmanite phase in post-spinel as a function of temperature at
380 27 GPa. The fit to the experimental results given by Yamazaki et al. (1996) is also shown for
381 comparison.

382 **Fig. 7.** BSE images (left) and grain size distributions (right) of the samples recovered from run
383 I1105 (2200 K, 5 min) with different starting materials (olivine powder, pre-sintered post-spinel,

384 olivine single crystal, and Fe-free forsterite single crystal). Because the four samples experience
385 exactly the same pressure, temperature, and duration conditions, they can be compared directly
386 with minimized uncertainty even though the differences of $\log d$ among them are not large. High
387 resolution BSE images are given in the online Supplementary Material.

388 **Fig. 8.** A comparison of grain sizes with different types of starting materials (olivine powder,
389 olivine single crystal, pre-synthesized post-spinel, and Fe-free forsterite single crystal) in run
390 I1147 (2 min), I1105 (5 min) and I1143 (300 min) and with forsterite powder from Yamazaki et al.
391 (1996).. Ol: San Carlos olivine. Fo: Fe-free forsterite.

392 **Fig. 9.** Grain sizes of bridgmanite at the topmost of the lower mantle for different temperatures
393 as a function of geological time. The grain sizes based on Yamazaki et al. (1996) are also shown
394 for comparison.

395

396 **Table 1:** A list of run conditions, results of bridgmanite grain sizes in the run products, and the growth
 397 rate. All experiments were performed at a pressure condition of 27 GPa. d : grain size. k : grain growth
 398 rate constant. IW: Fe-FeO buffer. The post-spinel is pre-synthesized from San Carlos olivine.

Run No.	T (K)	Duration (min)	f_{O_2} buffer	Sample	Analyzed BSE images	Analyzed grains (N)	$\log d$ (μm)	\bar{d} (μm)	k ($\mu\text{m}^n/\text{s}$)
I930-OI-R	2200	1000	IW	Post-spinel	5	756	0.23 (15)	1.72	2.77×10^{-4}
I951-OI-R	2200	10	IW	Post-spinel	3	843	-0.14 (15)	0.72	3.02×10^{-4}
I928-OI-R	2200	1.5	IW	Post-spinel	3	883	-0.38 (14)	0.42	1.22×10^{-4}
I959-OI-R	2200	100	IW	Post-spinel	3	474	-0.03 (11)	0.94	1.18×10^{-4}
I957-OI-R	1800	1000	IW	Post-spinel	3	365	-0.06 (13)	0.87	7.98×10^{-6}
I958-OI-R	2000	1000	IW	Post-spinel	3	369	0.07 (13)	1.17	3.85×10^{-5}
I956-OI-R	2000	10	IW	Post-spinel	4	916	-0.23 (15)	0.59	1.11×10^{-4}
I997-OI-R	2400	60	IW	Post-spinel	3	434	0.09 (14)	1.24	8.52×10^{-4}
I937-OI-R	1400	1000	IW	Post-spinel	3	304	-0.49 (12)	0.33	4.94×10^{-8}
I1023-OI	2200	100	IW	Post-spinel	3	447	0.03 (17)	1.08	2.44×10^{-4}
I1105 ^{*a}	2200	5	No	Olivine powder	5	340	-0.10 (13)	0.79	-- ^{*b}
				Post-spinel	4	397	-0.24 (15)	0.57	1.79×10^{-4}
				Olivine single crystal	4	320	-0.24 (13)	0.58	1.91×10^{-4}
				Forsterite single crystal	4	537	-0.33 (12)	0.47	5.30×10^{-5}
I1143 ^{*a}	2200	300	No	Olivine powder	4	327	0.09 (12)	1.24	-- ^{*b}
				Post-spinel	3	456	0.08 (8)	1.21	1.49×10^{-4}
				Forsterite single crystal	3	349	-0.02 (12)	0.95	4.29×10^{-5}
I1147 ^{*a}	2200	2	No	Olivine powder	4	364	-0.13 (15)	0.75	-- ^{*b}
				Post-spinel	3	318	-0.33 (12)	0.47	1.60×10^{-4}
				Forsterite single crystal	3	591	-0.43 (12)	0.38	3.83×10^{-5}

399 *a: two capsules (in total four samples) were loaded in these runs. The first capsule is filled with olivine powder
 400 without CsCl. The second capsule contains multiple samples, i.e., post-spinel, olivine single crystal, and Fe-free
 401 forsterite single crystal embedded in CsCl. Only the post-spinel sample in the second capsule was pre-synthesized.

402 *b: because the grain size exponent of the olivine powder samples is supposed to be affected by absorbed water,
 403 the k is not calculated here.

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Fig. 1.

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Fig. 2.

27 GPa, 2200 K, 1.5-1000 min

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 4

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Fig. 5

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Fig. 6

27 GPa, 2200 K, 5 min (I1105)

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Fig. 7

Fig. 8

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425

Fig. 9